

English Language Teacher Education with an Eco-Social Perspective: an Exploratory Study

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Abstract

The importance of a critical and eco-socially conscious English language teacher education in Europe is considered in this study. Information is collected through a survey to assess the working practice of various teachers and their perceptions of English language teaching under an eco-social lens. New avenues are then suggested to build a comprehensive eco-social language-teacher education program. Based on the survey responses of the different stakeholders participating in English language teacher education, our case study yielded a survey-based assessment of knowledge and familiarity with eco-social issues. Weaknesses relating to language teacher education with an eco-social perspective were detected and positive measures and strategies singled out, so as to design a language teacher education program with an eco-social perspective. In all, 345 responses collected in various European countries amassed data that reflected a positive attitude towards eco-social values among all the stakeholders within English language teacher education, mainly based on personal interests rather than collegial educational regulation. The need for the homogenization of existing resources and the regulation of education corpora was a common demand. Despite the limited scope of the survey, the results and the discussion presented in this paper offer a baseline study and a starting point to outline a fuller picture of the relation between English language teacher education and eco-social commitments.

Keywords: Teacher education; English language teaching; ecology; social challenges; environmental humanities

1. Introduction

In recent decades, generalized concern over the interaction between human beings and the world we inhabit has become an issue. Concern over negative human effects upon nature has given birth to a new concept, the Anthropocene, understood as an epoch “in which human beings, due to their activities [...] have become a geological force that is altering the earth’s composition and its ecosystems” (Pérez Ramos & Lindo Mañas, 2021, p. 17). The entanglements that sustain the mutual dependence of species and their habitats entail a cross-disciplinary shift within the humanities towards environmental and social concerns (Morán 2023; Peñaloza 2005). The global ecological crisis is evident when reflecting upon extreme climate change, biodiversity loss, and resource scarcity.

However, physical changes of that sort also interact with human development in dynamic ways. In that regard, the human development aspects of climate change are considered in the concept of Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSP),¹ and their related effects such as poverty, violent conflicts and migration movements, all of which are signs of a natural paradigm shift that confirm our dependency on planet Earth. This picture not only demands urgent action, but also projects our gaze into the future (González Reyes, 2018) to “foster the values needed to build a sustainable society and the new habits needed for environmental citizenship” (Nye *et al.*, 2013, p. 4).

Education, essential for social change (Butera *et al.* 2021), also determines our response to environmental challenges and strengthens stable and prosperous societies (Chawla & Cushing, 2007; Bengtsson, Barakat, Muttarak, Kebede & Lutz 2018). The European Commission places education “at the heart of Europe’s strategy for sustainable competitiveness and development” (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice 2015, p. 15), encourages quality education and training for all, and supports educational initiatives through action for a greener and more sustainable future because “there is a growing awareness and desire among young people to engage in sustainable development issues, particularly environmental and climate issues” (Council Recommendation of 16 June 2022 on learning for the green transition and sustainable development 2022/C 243/03).

Undoubtedly, the higher education area is a privileged site for “innovative and culturally-responsive transformations in teacher education practices” (Galvin *et al.* 2023), as well as for social transformation and new eco-pedagogical approaches that engage with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).² Environmental literacy, one of its various educational developments, fosters “the ability to recognise and critically evaluate local as well as global environmental practices and problems from various perspectives and across multiple scales of space and time and to react accordingly both as an individual and collectively” (Deetjen & Ludwig 2021, p.13). The field of English language teaching is an emergent area within which the eco-social perspective has recently been addressed (Goulah 2017; Mercer *et al.* 2022; Saiful 2014, 2023; Hauschild *et al.* 2012). As languages play a paramount role as transmitters of cultural values (Kramsch 1995), some recent proposals have embedded the ecological perspective in critical approaches to language teaching.³ It all suggests that language teacher education is key to sowing the seeds of an incarnated eco-social sensitivity or an “ecoethical consciousness”, as Martusewicz, Edmundson, & Lupinacci (2011) put it, among the future generations. In this study, the importance of a critical and eco-socially conscious English language teacher education in Europe is considered, drawing on data extracted from a consultation among relevant stakeholders to assess English language teachers’ practices, their perception of language teaching under an eco-social lens, and the avenues towards

¹ In a UN-commissioned report, three main channels were detected through which the inequality-aggravating effect of climate change can materialize, namely (a) an increase in the exposure of the disadvantaged groups to the adverse effects of climate change; (b) an increase in their susceptibility to damage caused by climate change; and (c) a decrease in their ability to cope and to recover from the damage climate change will inflict. See Islam and Winkel (2017), for a thorough analysis of the relationship between climate change and social inequality.

² It is only in recent studies (Alcantud-Díaz and Lloret-Catalá, 2023; Rodrigo-Mateu and Alcantud-Díaz, 2021) that the relation between SDGs and language teacher education has been explored. In particular, the issue of climate change and its social effects has not yet become a mainstream educational topic, despite the many UNESCO-organized education program actions. The alignment of language policy and planning for a sustainable world has only very recently become a matter of interest in some studies, such as Fettes (2023) and Silvhiany, Kurniawan, and Safrina (2024).

³ Marco A. Micalay-Hurtado and Robert Poole (2022) offered an interesting sample of ecolinguistic-informed pedagogical activities for English language instruction. As yet, no ecolinguistic-informed critical language approach towards language teacher education has, to the best of our knowledge, been published.

building a comprehensive eco-social language teacher education program that effectively fosters eco-social values within language teaching practice.

2. Rationale

Practitioners of all disciplines have striven to apply eco-social principles within the classroom with the aim of integrating sustainability, social justice, and democratic values in teaching practice, while promoting critical citizenship and ethical interdependence between the human and the natural world. According to Pulkki, Varpanen, and Mullen, the word eco-social is focused on “combining ecological and social questions to provide an impetus for building a sustainable society” (2021, p. 351). Most studies have been focused on the acquisition processes of students (Deetjen & Ludwig 2021; Nur, Anas & Pulu 2022; Silvhiany, Kurniawan & Safrina 2023), leaving the inclusion of eco-social issues at the discretion of language teachers. Something which poses a twofold obstacle. First, language teachers, regardless of their personal interest in the matter, frequently lack a solid knowledge of environmental and social issues. In addition to keeping themselves updated in their field of expertise, namely English language teaching, they have to make an extra effort to learn beyond their scope of duty, and they usually do so on their own initiative and in their free time. Second, acquaintance with eco-social issues and their inclusion in the English language classroom is often subject to the teachers’ ideology and their desire to act as agents of change for a more sustainable, inclusive, and greener future.⁴ In other words, being “innovative and eager to learn” characterizes their active role in the eco-social fields (Van der Heijden *et al.* 2015, p. 696), which is subject to personal interests and critical language awareness: “a perspective on teaching second, additional, heritage, or other languages that is based in values of social justice” (Crookes 2021, p. 247), rather than educational policies or guidelines.⁵ Both conditioning factors disclose a mismatch between the Council of the EU recommendations to member states to “align, in close cooperation with relevant stakeholders, strategies and plans in education and training with the green transition and sustainable development, including those related to curricula and assessment and educators’ initial training and continuing professional development” (Council of the European Union, 25 May 2022 2022/0004(NLE), p. 9) and actual practice, which is ultimately evidenced in the absence of a coherent and shared eco-social curriculum in language teacher education at a European level.

Only recently, following Iwan Syahril’s proposal for an interdisciplinary and multi-perspective approach to EFL teacher education programs, has the gap between language teacher education and teaching practice become an object of attention. In that study, the question of the literacy of future language teachers is widened to other disciplines, building on CLIL and content area literacy. However, it is at the cost of specific training in language teaching. Hence, our contention is that for an optimal language teacher

⁴ In a revealing case study, Jason Goulah (2017) showed that religious and ethical beliefs among refugee English language learners influenced their perspectives on climate-related and ecological crises. He concluded that ideology and ethical values on climate change intersected with language acquisition.

⁵ The Council of Europe (2002) has provided clear guidelines regarding positive and efficient strategies to promote diversity and intercultural communication in language teacher education, and the European Centre for Modern Languages (ECML) has also produced abundant materials on plurilingualism and CLIL available for download on their website. However, the issue of climate change and its social effects has not yet become a mainstream teacher education, despite the many actions in education programs undertaken by UNESCO. As the alignment of language policy and planning for a sustainable world has only become a matter of interest in very recent studies, *e.g.*, Fettes (2023) and Silvhiany, Kurniawan, and Safrina (2024), it can be deduced that interest in those issues among teachers stems from the personal, rather than the institutional realm.

education program with an eco-social perspective, a compromise between linguistic, pedagogical, and eco-social areas becomes essential.

Before addressing the task of designing an eco-social language teacher program, it was deemed important to ascertain the stakeholder views: future and current language teachers, educators, and policy makers. Data collection and analysis of responses are instrumental to detect any gaps that might exist in the relation between language teacher education and language teachers' actual teaching practices in relation to eco-social values. Knowledge of students, practitioners and educators' experiences and expectations might provide invaluable information to guide future actions. So, in the light of the above arguments and at the core of this study, there are three main research questions:

1. What are practitioners' perceptions of eco-social issues?
2. How do current and future language teachers and educators assess their access to resources and education to promote eco-social values within their classrooms?
3. What measures could be implemented to improve language teacher education with an eco-social input?

In the following sections, the design of an on-line survey administered to various stakeholders involved in language teacher education, gathering and interpreting the results, and discussing the major findings are all presented in detail.⁶

3. Method and Data Collection: Foreign language teaching with an eco-social perspective survey

Considering that research on language teacher education with an eco-social perspective is still in a very early phase and more field data are needed, it was decided to design an on-line survey to gather relevant information directly from the stakeholders engaged in the field of language teaching, because "surveys are ideal for documenting perceptions, attitudes, beliefs, or knowledge within a clear, predetermined sample of individuals" (Paradis *et al.* 2016, p. 263). As the on-line survey is a practical and easy-to-use instrument that can be widely disseminated and that yields immediate results, the "Foreign Language teaching with an eco-social perspective survey" was designed to collect information on the integration of eco-social contents and attitudes in language teaching within Europe.⁷ This tool, which can reach a large number of participants and that ensures anonymity, facilitates the collection of comparative data, the detection of critical issues in language teacher education, and the selection of methodological approaches, materials, and resources for further implementation.

The survey was anonymous to avoid bias. However, relevant personal data were gathered to obtain the main profiles of the stakeholders. To start with, the selection of current professional status offered choices between student teacher/graduate teacher of foreign languages; foreign language teacher/researcher at secondary/high school, language school, or university; teacher educator/trainer; education policy maker/public administrator. A list that provides a clear picture of the expertise of the participants within the field of language education. It was deemed important, to better assess their roles and scope of action, to define the stage of their career, and their function in educational

⁶ Considering that English is the most widely studied foreign language in European Union countries, and that it is within the field of expertise of the authors and their networks, the results of this survey should be interpreted in the context of teaching English as a foreign language.

⁷ Throughout this study, the term "foreign language" and "English language" are equatable. This assimilation responds to Vivian Cook's discussion on the teaching of English as a foreign language in Europe, where she insists that "the second/foreign distinction is past its sell-by date" and that any of those terms is instantly associated with the teaching of English as, "to a large extent then second/foreign/modern language teaching in most of Europe means the teaching of English" (2011: 141).

settings. In addition, age, gender and country of residence were items of interest that could also shed light on the profiles of the respondents.

Before disaggregating questions by professional status, all participants were asked about their personal concerns relating to issues of justice, democracy, and sustainability, and the role of languages as vehicles of cultural and social values. The purpose of those questions was to provide a complete picture of how student teachers of language, practitioners, educators, and policy makers faced the combination of language teaching with an eco-social perspective.

The next batch of questions for the participants who identified as student teachers addressed their personal training experience in eco-social issues and support received for the inclusion of eco-social issues within the language classroom. In the case of language teachers and teacher educators, interest was focused on their beliefs on the transformative role of teachers, and their assessments of personal experience combining language teaching with an eco-social perspective in their classrooms. Regarding policy makers, questions revolved around the importance of unifying language teacher education policies within Europe and their view of a joint curriculum for a European eco-social language teacher education.

Finally, all participants were asked to rate (on a scale of 1 not important/5 very important) a range of eight practical suggestions that could foster language teaching with an eco-social perspective. The different options included a digital repository with materials, surveys, studies, and scientific publications; a free on-line course with linguistic and eco-social contents to implement in the classroom; an open access interactive digital toolkit with best practices and resources; a handbook with policy orientations and suggested measures; a digital network of universities to share good practice and case studies; a network of eco-social schools and centers where student teachers can do their practical training; a European campaign on the importance of eco-social values and their inclusion in teacher education; and, the celebration of regular conferences and workshops on environmental humanities. In completion of that section, a dialog box was displayed to gather the respondents' comments and suggestions, so that they could freely add further suggestions and proposals complementing those in the questionnaire.⁸

The ultimate aim of the survey was to assess the participants' acquaintance with eco-social issues, detect weak spots regarding language teacher education with an eco-social perspective, and single out positive measures and strategies to advance language teacher education with an eco-social perspective. Once the survey had been designed, it was widely disseminated *via* email and digital channels and media sites. Communications activities targeted experienced teachers, lecturers, and educators, as well as English language student teachers from the authors' institution and their networks within Europe, including national TESOL communities and language education bodies, associations and platforms such as local Centers for Teacher Training and Educational Innovation (CFIE), the European Centre for Modern Languages (ECML), and the Electronic Platform for Adult Learning in Europe (EPALE), among others. The ultimate goal was to reach as many settings and professional status as possible in the field of language teaching and education to gather data representative of Europe's diversity and idiosyncrasy. The survey was open for a two-month period between November and December 2023, and collected a total of 345 responses from participants of all profiles. In the following section, all results and the major findings are presented and discussed.

⁸ The survey may be consulted in Annex 1.

4. Main findings and discussion

Regarding the nature of the sample and the profile of participants, the survey was aimed at a wide swathe of the language teaching community, working in education and practice. The majority of respondents identified as foreign language teachers/researchers at secondary/high school, language school, or university (56.8%). The groups formed of student teachers/graduated teachers of foreign languages, and teacher educators/trainers were equally represented and their responses amounted to 40% of all responses, while education policy makers/public administrators accounted for 3%. Those data indicated a prevalence of practitioners among the respondents. Likewise, the most relevant age groups were between 39 and 59 years old, which amounted to 65% of all the participants. In total, 84.7% of the whole sample had worked for over 10 years. In terms of gender, an overwhelming 84.3% of all respondents identified as female, which confirmed a prevalent feminization of the language teaching profession, a feature already detected in previous findings (Barros-del Río, 2023; Drudy, 2008). All in all, the data showed a bias in the professional profile of participants with language teachers as the largest responding group and underrepresentation of the student teacher, teacher educator, and especially policy maker, and public administrator cohorts. Regarding the geographical scope of the survey, most responses were from European countries such as Portugal (48%), Romania (15.9%), Spain (15.4%), Lithuania (9.3%) and Greece (6.1%). Other responses were from Finland, Italy, Bulgaria, *etc.*, in order of importance, with a total representation of 49 countries from both within and outside of Europe. Although the initial geographical scope of the survey was within Europe, the data showed a geographical bias with a significant representation of participants from Southern Europe, despite a careful dissemination strategy designed to reach organizations of relevance to language teachers. That limitation, which correlated with the authors' previous research contacts and networks, provided a limited diagnosis that nonetheless generated interesting results. In a second stage of the survey, respondents' attitudes towards eco-social issues and the way in which they related eco-social aspects with their professional practice were examined. When asked about the relation between languages and cultural values, including eco-social aspects, the vast majority of student teachers (98.6%) considered languages as vehicles for cultural and/or social values. Furthermore, 78% of the cohort admitted to concern over issues of justice, democracy, and sustainability, and 88% considered that language teaching should incorporate eco-social contents and values such as inclusion, natural environment preservation, diversity, democracy, and sustainability. However, less than half (42%) reported frequent or regular use of curricular materials that merged contents on democracy and sustainability during their academic training, as shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Use of eco-social curricular materials in language teacher education.

Finally, a vast majority (94%) believed that eco-social values that are introduced in the teaching of a foreign language could make a positive change in the world. The overall results showed a genuine interest in eco-social values among student teachers of languages, arguably a young population group, in spite of their relative low exposure to specific training. Accordingly, the role of education as a transformative instrument was highly valued by this group of participants. Data gathered from language teachers, most of whom were experienced teachers, showed a slightly different picture. Together with language student teachers, this cohort believed that languages are vehicles for cultural and/or social values (97.4%) and even though most of them (85%) were in favor of using materials that included contents on democracy and sustainability, a little over half (56.7%) did so on a regular basis and slightly over one third (34.2%) did so occasionally, as illustrated in Figure 2:

Figure 2. Use of eco-social materials in the foreign language classroom.

Among this cohort, a high percentage (88%) believed that the inclusion of eco-social values in the teaching of a foreign language would make a positive change, however only a smaller proportion (67%) viewed themselves as agents of change. These results reveal positive perceptions among language teachers, most of whom in this study were female, towards eco-social issues. They reflect the attitudes towards welfare and climate change policies of the profile of an average European citizen:

Eco-social policies are most likely to be supported by women living in big cities, who have a high level of education but feel less satisfied with their income, who highly trust public institutions and have strong egalitarian ideas that are often claimed as being left-wing (Otto & Gugushvili 2020: 13).

However, the results of this survey have disclosed an imbalance between belief and practice in the language teaching practice, depending on the respondents' profile. General awareness of the cultural load embedded in languages contrasts with low effective teaching practices and lack of resources and skills on the topics in question. These shortcomings suggest an insufficient or ineffective initial and life-long training of language teachers and point to the need to enrich education programs with eco-social content and appropriate pedagogical strategies. The survey also showed that language teachers' self-perception as effective agents of change was less positive than that of student teachers' (67% versus 94%). That significant difference was correlated with the less utopic and more pragmatic attitudes of the older rather than the younger cohorts. As contended in some studies, novice teachers have expressed stronger belief in the role of

the teacher than more experienced ones (Georgious, 2008). Added to that, years of experience may have provided a broader view of the teaching profession as a practice that also covers greater managerial and administrative burdens and a poorer social image (Carlo *et al.* 2013).

The vast majority (97%) of teacher educators and trainers also believed that languages were vehicles for cultural and/or social values. Likewise, 82% thought that the teaching of languages was an optimal means to introduce eco-social contents and most of them (88%) thought that the inclusion of eco-social values within foreign language teaching could lead to positive change. This positive attitude towards the power of languages as transformative tools may be contrasted with less enthusiastic perceptions of their role as agents of change (76%). The teachers and educators also admitted that only 56% had used curricular materials that included contents on democracy and sustainability on a regular basis and 30.4% had used them sometimes, as shown in Figure 3:

Figure 3. Use of eco-social materials among teacher educators and trainers.

Similar to other cohorts, such a low rate contrasted with their willingness to use materials of that sort, which amounted to 77%. All in all, those figures matched the ones gathered from language teachers and confirmed a general awareness of eco-social values within language teaching and teacher education. However, the data also showed that practical implementation was significantly less effective and unbalanced depending on territory. It is a question that adds some interesting insight into the inherent differences in training programmes across Europe and points to a lack of coherence and common guidelines. According to the data gathered from the survey, university professors within countries such as Portugal or Romania were more inclined to use materials of that sort than their counterparts in other countries. Similarly, 59% of Portuguese teachers and students and 43% of Romanian teachers and students claimed that they used eco-social materials frequently, whereas in Spain a relatively high percentage (31%) responded that they rarely or never used them. This scenario unveils a lack of appropriate training and materials, and/or difficulties in accessing existing resources depending on location. Also, the data suggested that comprehensive training programs that incorporate eco-social values could affect teaching practice and encourage practitioners to use materials and contents on democratic values and sustainability. In other words, the lack of European convergence in language teacher education has resulted in different sorts of training with regard to eco-social values. Hence, sensitivity towards those issues to some extent depends on the practitioners' country of residence, to the detriment of the European value of equality.

With regard to data provided by policy makers and public administrators, all of them considered that languages are vehicles for cultural and/or social values and a majority

(90%) admitted that teacher education in Europe needs more cohesion and convergence. A considerable number (80%) voted in favor of convergence of language teacher education in Europe. They believed that embedded eco-social values could foster cohesion, inclusivity and green internationalization, and all of them affirmed their willingness to support the creation of joint curricula in higher education institutions where the linguistic, the environmental, and the social fields merged. When asked about possible solutions to the current situation, a majority (72.7%) found that a package of recommendations and guidelines for a more socially inclusive, critically engaged, and environmentally conscious foreign language teacher education framework in Europe could be useful, as shown in Figure 4:

Figure 4. Policy makers and administrators' interest in common guidelines.

In the third and final section of the survey, all profiles were offered a battery of practical solutions to rate in order of importance. Among the options proposed, a free on-line course with linguistic and eco-social materials to implement in the classroom, an open access interactive digital toolkit for the eco-social language teacher with best practices and resources, and a digital repository with materials, surveys, studies and scientific publications on eco-social and linguistic topics, were the highest rated actions, as shown in Figure 5:

Figure 5. Preferences on practical solutions.

These choices speak of a pressing need for training and support materials and resources, so that an eco-social perspective can be more easily instilled in the daily

practice of language teaching. Along similar lines, the participants' comments and proposals suggested the grouping of existing materials within integrated and unified repositories, the creation of a communication tool (newsletter) to disseminate news, courses and resources on the topic, spaces for sharing best practices and experiences, and assessment tools, and the creation of a free webinar or an official cross-curricular subject for educational purposes. Also, caution over Internet access within some schools and countries was mentioned.

In general terms, the survey revealed positive attitudes towards eco-social values among the language teacher education stakeholders, which stemmed from their personal interests rather than from collegial educational regulation. Laying stress upon eco-social contents is generally left in the hands of practitioners, which adds to an already burgeoning workload. Even so, all the groups found the topics relevant and a significant percentage managed to include them in their daily practice. The need for greater homogenization of existing resources and the regulation of education corpora was a common demand among many teachers. The shortcomings suggested that for a more comprehensive and balanced report of the relation between eco-social values and language teacher education, a wider and more balanced representation of participants would be advisable. It could be achieved with a more target-oriented communication strategy which, in the case of student teachers would require the active involvement of teacher educators. On their part, the policy makers and public administrators' cohort should count with the help of national and European administrative bodies. Despite the limited scope of this survey, the results of this baseline study are a starting point to outline a more complete picture of the relation between language teacher education and eco-social commitments.

5. Conclusions

There has been increasing interest in the eco-social ramifications of the humanities which includes the teaching of languages. European guidelines are also moving in that direction, despite a lack of specific convergent measures that is hindering working practice. Although language teaching practitioners manage to include eco-social values at their own discretion, using CLIL and other strategies in their daily teaching, there has been scant little research into English language teacher education, which might be an initial step towards training responsible practitioners. Therefore, an eco-social survey on language teacher education has been used to gather data on the perceptions of practitioners with regard to eco-social issues, their access to appropriate resources and educational materials, and their demands for improvement of the current situation, in order to assess and to analyze the needs that present and future English language teachers within Europe have shared.

After massive dissemination of the online survey, 345 responses were collected mostly from practitioners, but also from prospective teachers of languages and policy makers. The collected data revealed the following main findings: First, personal concern with eco-social issues is mostly embedded in language teaching practice, yet this effort stems from the practitioners' own initiative rather than from a negotiated and common educational policy. So, practitioners lack a coherent body of guiding principles and they strive to find appropriate supporting materials and best practice guidelines. Second, language teacher education with an eco-social perspective should be a life-long learning task and universally accessible. It points to the need for online and open-access materials that can be easily updated in rapidly changing contexts. Third, a wide range of disparate and miscellaneous materials together with a lack of selection criteria frequently result in low-effective practices, according to practitioners. It suggests that unified and

internationally regulated corpora together with a consensual language teacher education program could promote cohesion, inclusivity and green internationalization in language teaching practice. In summary, some practical measures to display might include tailored on-line courses, digital toolkits with best practices and resources, and digital repositories with materials, studies, and publications at the disposal of practitioners. Based on our initial findings, future steps could follow a twofold path: first, the creation of an interactive toolkit with a comprehensive collection of learning materials, open education resources, methodological guidelines and examples of best practices for an eco-social language teacher practitioner. Second, the design of a handbook for policy makers and education bodies with policy orientations and guidelines for curriculum convergence in the field of language teacher education. The authors of this paper are currently seeking funding for an international research project.

Despite the limited scope of this study and the detected shortcomings, conclusions lead to the need for a comprehensive and unified eco-social language teacher education program. Although the recommendations presented here stem from the intersection of the eco-social and language teaching fields, inter-disciplinary convergence and homogenization are urgently needed in the higher education area. The proposals that have been suggested could be replicated in each of the disciplines, so that a more comprehensive eco-social view of instruction can continue gaining ground in the humanities.

Declaration of interest statement

No potential conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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